

Non-Gaussian statistics of concentration fluctuations in free liquid diffusion

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We show that the three-point skewness of concentration fluctuations is nonvanishing in free liquid diffusion, even in the limit of vanishingly small mean concentration gradients. We exploit a high-Schmidt reduction of non-linear Landau-Lifshitz hydrodynamics for a binary fluid, both analytically and by a massively parallel Lagrangian Monte Carlo simulation. Non-Gaussian statistics result from nonlinear coupling of concentration fluctuations to thermal velocity fluctuations, analogous to the turbulent advection of a passive scalar. Concentration fluctuations obey no central limit theorem, counter to the predictions of macroscopic fluctuation theory for generic diffusive systems.

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Introduction. The origin of macroscopic hydrodynamics from microscopic molecular dynamics is a vexing open problem in physics, with various competing proposals such as Zwanzig-Mori coarse-graining methods [1,2], hydrodynamic scaling limit (HSL) [3] and macroscopic fluctuation theory (MFT) [4], renormalization group (RG) [5] and effective field theory (EFT) [6], or kinetic theory for low-density gases [7]. The problem became even more complex with the theoretical discovery [8] and experimental verification [9] of generic spatial long-range nonequilibrium correlations. Such second-order correlations are predicted by linearized fluctuating hydrodynamics [10] and have been interpreted in MFT as central limit theorem (CLT) corrections to a leading-order law of large numbers. Important topics of ongoing research are the dynamical emergence of these correlations [11] and the higher-order correlations [4,12], especially as the latter can be measured experimentally in some condensed-matter systems, such as atomic superfluids [13]. Indeed, the universal validity of MFT has been challenged by the prediction of non-Gaussian statistics of charge density fluctuations in Dirac metals based on nonlinear fluctuating hydrodynamics [14], with higher statistics different from MFT predictions for generic diffusive systems [12].

In this Letter, we show that non-Gaussian statistics appear already in a very commonplace example: the free diffusion of a solute in a liquid solvent, such as a drop of dye in water. Long-range correlations in free liquid diffusion were long ago observed in terrestrial experiments by light

scattering [15]. Although quenched at large scales by buoyancy effects on Earth, they are observed up to system size in ongoing low-gravity space experiments [16,17]. The concentration second-order correlations were successfully predicted by linearized fluctuating hydrodynamics [18] and fluctuations are thus widely expected to be Gaussian [19]. However, in a landmark work [20], Donev, Fai, and Vanden-Eijnden (hereafter, DFV) succeeded to explain these fluctuations in a liquid at rest by a nonlinear advection equation $\partial_t c + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla c = D_0 \Delta c$, where c is the concentration of the solute, \mathbf{u} is the thermal velocity field of the solvent liquid governed by linearized fluctuating hydrodynamics, and D_0 is the bare diffusivity. In agreement with the EFT interpretation, there is an explicit high-wave-number cutoff in this model taken to be on the order of the radius σ of the solute molecule. In the limit of high Schmidt number $\nu/D_0 \gg 1$ appropriate to most liquid mixtures, DFV showed that this system reduces to a version of the Kraichnan model of turbulent scalar advection [21,22]:

$$\partial_t c + \mathbf{w} \circ \nabla c = D_0 \Delta c, \quad (1)$$

where \circ denotes the Stratonovich product and \mathbf{w} is a Gaussian random velocity with zero mean and covariance $\langle w_i(\mathbf{x}, t) w_j(\mathbf{x}', t') \rangle = R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \delta(t - t')$, where $\mathbf{R} = \frac{2k_B T}{\eta} \mathbf{G}$, with \mathbf{G} the Green's function of the Stokes operator (Oseen tensor). The DFV theory leads naturally to a renormalization of the bare diffusivity D_0 , so that the mean concentration field satisfies a Fickian diffusion equation $\partial_t \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t) = D \Delta_x \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, in which the diffusivity at macroscopic scales is given by the Stokes-Einstein relation $D = k_B T / 6\pi \eta \sigma \gg D_0$, where T is temperature and $\eta = \rho \nu$ the shear viscosity of the solvent. DFV explained the emergence of long-range correlations as closely analogous to a turbulent cascade of an advected scalar. Just as in the Kraichnan model [22], closed equations hold

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \mathcal{C}_{12} = & D(\Delta_{\mathbf{x}_1} + \Delta_{\mathbf{x}_2}) \mathcal{C}_{12} + \frac{1}{2} R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \nabla_{x_1^i} \nabla_{x_2^j} \mathcal{C}_{12} \\ & + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \nabla_{x_1^i} \bar{c}_1 \nabla_{x_2^j} \bar{c}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

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for second cumulants $C_{12} = C(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, t)$, also

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t C_{123} = & D[\Delta_{\mathbf{x}_1} + \Delta_{\mathbf{x}_2} + \Delta_{\mathbf{x}_3}]C_{123} \\ & + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)\nabla_{x_i'}\nabla_{x_j'}C_{123} + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_3)\nabla_{x_i'}\nabla_{x_j'}C_{123} \\ & + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_2 - \mathbf{x}_3)\nabla_{x_i'}\nabla_{x_j'}C_{123} \\ & + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2)[\nabla_{x_i'}\bar{c}_1\nabla_{x_j'}C_{23} + \nabla_{x_j'}\bar{c}_2\nabla_{x_i'}C_{13}] \\ & + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_3)[\nabla_{x_i'}\bar{c}_1\nabla_{x_j'}C_{23} + \nabla_{x_j'}\bar{c}_3\nabla_{x_i'}C_{12}] \\ & + R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_2 - \mathbf{x}_3)[\nabla_{x_i'}\bar{c}_2\nabla_{x_j'}C_{13} + \nabla_{x_j'}\bar{c}_3\nabla_{x_i'}C_{12}] \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

for triple cumulants $C_{123} = C(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3, t)$ of concentration fluctuations, and so forth. In these equations, gradients of the lower-order cumulants appear as source terms. It was shown recently [23] that the DFV model yields second-order correlations in the form observed experimentally [15,24]: $C_{12} \propto |\nabla\bar{c}(t)|^2\sigma r_{12}$, where $\nabla\bar{c}(t)$ is the mean concentration gradient and $r_{12} = |\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2|$.

It was pointed out also in Ref. [23] that the higher-order cumulants of concentration fluctuations should not vanish in the DFV theory, just as they do not in turbulent scalar cascades. The structure of the source terms in the closed equations (2), (3), etc. suggests that, in general, the P th-order cumulant $C_{12\dots P} \propto (\nabla\bar{c})^P$. If so, not only are cumulants for all $P > 2$ nonvanishing, but also when normalized by the $P/2$ power of the second cumulant they will remain nonzero in the limit $|\nabla\bar{c}| \rightarrow 0$. Such higher cumulants nondimensionalized by the second cumulant generalize the concepts of skewness and kurtosis, and their nonvanishing indicates persistent non-Gaussianity as $|\nabla\bar{c}| \rightarrow 0$. A main assumption of MFT [4] is that macroscopic diffusion equations arise as a ‘‘law of large numbers’’ in a hydrodynamic scaling limit [3] where macroscopic gradients become arbitrarily weak on the microscopic scale. The experimentally observed second cumulants of concentration fluctuations are then interpreted in MFT as ‘‘central limit theorem’’ corrections, predicted to become Gaussian in the limit [3,4].

To address these questions, we consider here the simplest situation [23] with initial concentration profile $c_0(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{c_0}{2}(1 + \operatorname{erf}(\frac{z}{2\sqrt{D\tau}}))$ in infinite three-dimensional space and gradients nonzero only in the z direction. The parameter τ with units of time is introduced to set the magnitude of the initial concentration gradient as $|\nabla c_0| = c_0/\sqrt{4\pi D\tau}$. Our problem setup idealizes laboratory experiments [15,24] on free diffusion with initial interfaces in concentration, but where the spatial domain was finite and gravity appeared. Following DFV, we ignore initial local equilibrium fluctuations of concentration, which are orders of magnitude smaller than the nonequilibrium fluctuations of interest (see Fig. 2 from Ref. [15]). Note that the mean concentration $\bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ obtained by evolving the error function profile under the diffusion equation keeps the same form, but with $\tau \mapsto t + \tau$. To probe the non-Gaussian statistics, we will calculate the three-point skewness function $\mathcal{S}_{123} = C_{123}/(C_{13}C_{23}C_{12})^{1/2}$.

We focus first on the early-time, transient regime when non-equilibrium correlations begin to emerge. In fact, in the free-decay problem where the mean gradient decreases in time as $|\nabla\bar{c}| \sim c_0/\sqrt{4\pi D(t + \tau)}$, the largest cumulants in absolute magnitude appear near the end of this early-time regime [25]

and thus should present the largest experimental signal. This early-time regime was first investigated theoretically by DFV [20] whose results for the spectral structure function of concentration were confirmed in physical space to have the form [25]

$$\begin{aligned} C(r_{12}, \theta_{12}, Z_{12}, t) & \simeq \frac{3c_0^2}{8\pi} \times \frac{\sigma}{r_{12}}(1 + \cos^2\theta_{12}) \\ & \times \left[E_1\left(\frac{Z_{12}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{12}^2}{2D(t + \tau)}\right) - E_1\left(\frac{Z_{12}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{12}^2}{2D\tau}\right) \right], \quad (4) \\ Dt & \lesssim \sigma^2 \ll r^2, \end{aligned}$$

where r_{12}, θ_{12} are spherical coordinates (omitting azimuthal angle) of the separation vector $\mathbf{r}_{12} = \mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2$ of the two points, $Z_{12} = (z_1 + z_2)/2$ is the mean of their vertical positions, $z_{12} = r_{12} \cos\theta_{12}$ is the vertical coordinate of \mathbf{r}_{12} , and $E_1(x)$ is the exponential integral function (see Eq. (6.6.1) of Ref. [26]). The result (4) is derived from Eq. (2) by a short-time, large- r asymptotic expansion in which the source term is evaluated with the infinite-space Oseen tensor $G_{ij} = \frac{1}{8\pi r}(\delta_{pq} + \frac{r_i r_j}{r^2})$ and treated as the leading term on the right-hand side, the diffusion term being regarded as a small perturbation. Formula (4) then results from direct time integration of the source term. The triple cumulant C_{123} can be evaluated in the analogous asymptotic scheme. With the symmetries of the interface problem, the triple cumulant is specified at each time t by the triangle in \mathbb{R}^3 with vertices $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3$ or, more geometrically, by the lengths of its three sides r_{13}, r_{23}, r_{12} , by two Euler angles β, γ specifying its orientation, and by the vertical position $Z = z_3$ (see Sec. A of the Supplemental Material [27]). The asymptotic solution for short times $Dt \lesssim \sigma^2$ and large triangles $\min_{p,q} R_{pq} \gg \sigma$ is obtained by integrating in time the six source terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (3), treating the diffusion terms as a perturbation. Although the calculation is straightforward in principle, the resulting expression for C_{123} is quite lengthy. See Sec. A of the Supplemental Material for details of the derivation and the full analytical result [27].

Especially relevant to the validity of a central limit theorem is C_{123} in the weak-gradient limit $|\nabla c_0| \rightarrow 0$ or, equivalently, $\tau \rightarrow \infty$. The analytical expressions simplify in that limit so that, for example, the result analogous to Eq. (4) for general particle pair p, q becomes [25]

$$\begin{aligned} C(r_{pq}, \theta_{pq}, Z_{pq}, t) & \simeq \frac{3}{2}\sigma Dt \frac{|\nabla c_0|^2}{r_{pq}}(1 + \cos^2\theta_{pq}), \\ D\tau & \gg \max\{r_{pq}^2, Z_{pq}^2\} \gg \sigma^2 \gtrsim Dt. \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

The latter conditions for all pairs p, q guarantee not only that $\sigma|\nabla c_0|/c_0 \ll 1$ but also that the triangle with vertices $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3$ lies entirely in the interface region where the mean concentration gradient $\sim |\nabla c_0|$ is nearly a space-time constant. The time integrals of the six forcing terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (3) can be computed in the same manner, yielding $C_{123} \propto |\nabla c_0|^3(\sigma Dt)^2/r^3$ (where r is some combination of r_{13}, r_{23}, r_{12} depending on β, γ), so that skewness $\mathcal{S}_{123} \propto (\sigma Dt/r^3)^{1/2}$ is growing in time and independent of $|\nabla c_0|$, even as $|\nabla c_0| \rightarrow 0$. See Appendix A for a sketch of

FIG. 1. Triple cumulants for the vertical equilateral triangle with side lengths $r^* = 50$ and for initial mean concentration profiles with $\tau^* = 10^4, 10^6, 10^8,$ and 10^{10} going from left to right, top to bottom, respectively. Solid lines with symbols and shades show the numerical results and corresponding errors from the Lagrangian Monte Carlo computation. Dashed lines correspond to the analytical expression (Sec. A of the Supplemental Material [27]), valid asymptotically for short times, as highlighted by the insets. For corresponding results on the combined second cumulant $(C_{13}C_{23}C_{12})^{1/2}$ used to calculate the three-point skewness, see Appendix B, Fig. 4.

the calculation and Sec. A of the Supplemental Material for full details [27].

These conclusions may be confirmed and extended by an independent evaluation of the concentration cumulants with a Lagrangian Monte Carlo method, first employed for passive scalars in the Kraichnan model of turbulent advection [28–30] and recently applied by us to liquid mixing [25]. In this method, the DFV model (1) is solved for $D_0 = 0$ at the three points \mathbf{x}_p , $p = 1, 2, 3$, in one realization of the thermal velocity \mathbf{w} by setting $c(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\xi_p(t))$, where $d\xi_p/dt = \mathbf{w}_p$, $\xi_p(0) = \mathbf{x}_p$, $p = 1, 2, 3$, with $\mathcal{W} = (\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \mathbf{w}_3)$ a nine-dimensional Gaussian white noise with covariance

$$\langle w_{pi}(t)w_{qj}(t') \rangle_{\xi} = R_{ij}(\xi_p(t), \xi_q(t))\delta(t - t'), \quad (6)$$

for $p, q = 1, \dots, 3$ and $i, j = 1, \dots, 3$. By repeating this numerical integration for independent realizations $\mathcal{W}^{(n)}$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, the triple cumulant can then be evaluated by an empirical average over samples

$$C_{123} \simeq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t) c'^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t) c'^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_3, t), \quad (7)$$

where $c'^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. This scheme yields the exact cumulants without restriction to short times and larger, but it is subject to slow Monte Carlo convergence and can require a large number N of samples. In the original

application to turbulent advection [28–30], a number of samples $N \simeq 10^7$ sufficed, but our problem is much more demanding. First, the correlations between thermal velocity fluctuations decay with distance, opposite to the growing correlations for turbulent velocities. Second, we consider a problem of free decay rather than a statistical steady state as in the turbulence studies [28–30], and the decaying mean concentration field generates higher cumulants with absolute magnitude decreasing in time. For these reasons, accurate results for our case required $N \simeq 10^{14}$ samples, which we only achieved by a CUDA-MPI (Compute Unified Device Architecture library combined with Message Passing Interface paradigms) implementation designed to leverage the massive parallel-processing capabilities of GPUs (Graphic Processing Units). For more details on the numerics, see Ref. [25] and Sec. B of the Supplemental Material [27]. All results are calculated in dimensionless form, with $r^* = r/\sigma$, $t^* = 2Dt/\sigma^2$, and $c^* = c/c_0$.

We present in Fig. 1 the triple cumulant C_{123}^* at three points forming an equilateral triangle with side length $r_{13}^* = r_{23}^* = r_{12}^* = 50$ and lying in a plane perpendicular to $z = 0$ ($\gamma = 0, \beta = \pi/2$). (Results for another value $r^* = 100$ are presented in Sec. C of the Supplemental Material, which lead to the same conclusions [27]). The Lagrangian numerical results for four values of $\tau^* = 10^4$ – 10^{10} are seen generally to grow in magnitude with t^* and then roughly to saturate, within increasing Monte Carlo error. They agree well with

FIG. 2. Three-point skewness for the vertical equilateral triangle with side lengths $r^* = 50$ and small concentration gradients. [Colors and symbols are coded as in Fig. 1 for $\tau^* = 10^6$ (cyan squares), 10^8 (green circles), and 10^{10} (yellow triangles), The result for $\tau^* = 10^4$ can be found in Sec. C of the Supplemental Material [27]]. Solid lines with symbols and shades represent the numerical Lagrangian results and Monte Carlo errors, while dashed lines show the analytical prediction. The times t in seconds on the upper axis are calculated with reference values $\sigma = 10$ nm and $D = 2.2 \times 10^{-5}$ mm²/s for which the maximum skewness is achieved in about 4 ms. Short-time behavior is enlarged in the inset, with the red line showing the short-time asymptotic prediction for vanishing concentration gradient.

the analytic predictions for shorter t^* , as seen especially in the insets. The nonvanishing triple cumulants demonstrate non-Gaussianity of the concentration statistics. Note the intriguing change in sign between $\tau^* = 10^4$ and $\tau^* = 10^6$. For $\tau^* > 10^6$, however, the triple cumulants appear to become qualitatively similar and simply decreasing in magnitude with increasing τ^* , consistent with the estimate $C_{123} \propto |\nabla c_0|^3$. The latter scaling is confirmed by the plot of the three-point skewness S_{123} in Fig. 2, in which the results for the three largest τ values, differing over four orders of magnitude, essentially collapse. Note that the skewness from the Lagrangian Monte Carlo also agrees well with the asymptotic prediction at short t^* (inset) but thereafter attains a maximum value of about 0.01 and then slowly decreases in t^* , possibly to a nonzero quasisteady value. Our main conclusion is unaffected if the skewness vanishes as $t^* \rightarrow \infty$ but, crucially, it is essentially τ independent, not only in the early-time regime but over the entire t^* range studied. Thus, there is no central limit theorem with zero skewness in the limit of vanishing gradients, $\nabla c_0 \rightarrow 0$. Figure 2 constitutes the main result of this Letter.

We have thus shown that nonlinear Landau-Lifschitz fluctuating hydrodynamics for a binary mixture, in the high-Schmidt limit appropriate to liquid diffusion, implies non-Gaussian statistics of concentration fluctuations. An experimental test of these predictions might be feasible by light-scattering methods [31,32]. We have considered free diffusion of an initial inhomogeneous concentration field, but it would be interesting to investigate also nonequilibrium steady states. Beyond correlations, other statistics could show turbulentlike, non-Gaussian features such as fat tails in probability density functions (PDFs) [33]. Note, however, that this can occur only for multipoint variables such as

concentration increments, as the PDF of the single-point concentration indeed becomes Gaussian as $\nabla c_0 \rightarrow 0$: see Appendices and more comparisons with turbulence (Sec. D of the Supplemental Material [27]). Buoyancy effects of gravity that are known to quench long-range concentration correlations can be incorporated into the DFV model [20] and it is worth understanding their influence on non-Gaussianity. In low-gravity environments, in contrast, thermal noise effects are observed to propagate to the system size and thus non-Gaussian statistics occurring in liquid diffusion may have critical importance for space exploration [17].

Our results contradict the naïve expectations of MFT that statistics of fluctuations should become Gaussian in the limit of weak gradients. These predictions of MFT are rigorous central limit theorem results for simple toy models of particle diffusion, such as Kawasaki lattice gases, in a suitable “hydrodynamic scaling limit” [3,4]. However, it is not at all clear how to formulate a “hydrodynamic scaling limit” for the problem of liquid diffusion and recent work has shown that the HSL, even when mathematically applicable in principle, may be physically unattainable [34,35]. Furthermore, the DFV model accurately predicts other effects missed by MFT, such as renormalization of the bare diffusivity [20,36] that is commonly observed in molecular dynamics studies [37,38]. The latter renormalization as well as the non-Gaussian statistics calculated in the present study is due to nonlinear coupling of the diffusive mode with the momentum mode, which is a general phenomenon predicted by renormalization group [5] but not included in MFT analyses of diffusion [4]. It was a fundamental insight of the Kraichnan model that relative advection even by a Gaussian velocity field, such as thermal velocity fluctuations in this study, will produce non-Gaussian multipoint statistics for the advected scalar [21,22]. The non-Gaussian diffusive statistics predicted in Dirac fluids arise from a similar mechanism [14]. The magnitude of the skewness that we observe is not large (only 0.01 at maximum in the case considered in Fig. 2) but nonvanishing as $\nabla c_0 \rightarrow 0$, indicating persistent nonlinear coupling of concentration and velocity fluctuations. We have thus confirmed and extended the claims of earlier work that “nonequilibrium fluctuations do not represent merely a perturbation of a macroscopic state” [20,39,40]. Our results imply that MFT and HSL cannot be a universally valid explanation for origin of hydrodynamic behavior, not even for the familiar example of liquid diffusion.

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FIG. 3. Illustration of the triangle formed by vertices \mathbf{x}_1 , \mathbf{x}_2 , \mathbf{x}_3 in reference position in the horizontal plane.

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Data Availability. The data that support the findings of this article are openly available [41].

Appendix A: Sketch of analytical computation of triple cumulants. We give here a brief sketch of the calculation of the triple cumulant of the concentration fluctuations, asymptotically for large separations and for short times. We refer to Fig. 3 for a sketch of the three points in the triple cumulant, forming the vertices of a triangle in the plane perpendicular to the mean gradient. The triangle is shown in the reference position that we adopt, before rotation by Euler angles β , γ into general orientation. The side lengths r_{13} , r_{23} , r_{12} and the interior angles ψ_{13} , ψ_{23} , ψ_{12} specify the geometry of the triangle. The source terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (3) for the triple cumulant that arise from gradients of the mean and second cumulant of the concentration depend on both the geometry of the triangle and its orientation and displacement along the gradient. The latter dependencies appear in the second cumulant C_{pq} through the azimuthal angle θ_{pq} and the mean displacement Z_{pq} , which ultimately can all be calculated knowing the geometry, orientation, and displacement of the triangle. Using these variables and the symmetries of the problem, the six source terms can all be calculated; for example, the first one, $F_{123} = R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2) \nabla_{x_i} \bar{c}_1 \nabla_{x_j} C_{23}$, becomes

$$F_{123} = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r_{12}} \bar{c}'(z_1) \left\{ (\cos\theta_{23} - \cos\psi_{13} \cos\theta_{12}) \frac{\partial C_{23}}{\partial r_{23}} + \frac{\sin^2\theta_{23} + \cos\theta_{12}(\cos\theta_{12} + \cos\psi_{13} \cos\theta_{23})}{r_{23}} \frac{\partial C_{23}}{\partial(\cos\theta_{23})} + \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos^2\theta_{12}) \frac{\partial C_{23}}{\partial Z_{23}} \right\},$$

and similarly for all six source terms.

Following the asymptotic scheme outlined in the main text for the second cumulant, the leading-order contribution to the triple cumulant for large separations and short times is obtained simply by integrating in time the contributions from these six source terms. We here discuss only the simplifications that occur in the time $\tau \rightarrow \infty$. First, the mean concentration gradient becomes t independent to leading order: $\nabla \bar{c} \sim \nabla c_0 \sim c_0 / \sqrt{4\pi D \tau}$. In that case, one must evaluate time integrals only of the derivatives of the second cumulants. These are easily evaluated for large τ from Eq. (5) to be

$$\int_0^t \frac{\partial C}{\partial r_{pq}}(r_{pq}, \cos\theta_{pq}, Z_{pq}, s) ds \sim -\frac{3}{4} |\nabla c_0|^2 \frac{\sigma}{r_{pq}^2} (1 + \cos^2\theta_{pq}) D t^2$$

and

$$\int_0^t \frac{\partial C}{\partial(\cos\theta_{pq})}(r_{pq}, \cos\theta_{pq}, Z_{pq}, s) ds \sim \frac{3}{2} |\nabla c_0|^2 \frac{\sigma}{r_{pq}} \cos\theta_{pq} D t^2,$$

with other contributions asymptotically smaller. Combining the contributions from the six source terms and recalling that $D = k_B T / 6\pi\eta\sigma$, one obtains $C_{123} \propto |\nabla c_0|^3 (\sigma D t)^2 / r^3$ as claimed in the main text. It follows from this result that the three-point skewness \mathcal{S}_{123} will remain finite in the limit of weak gradients or $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, at least for the large-separation, short-time regime. See Sec. A of the Supplemental Material for complete details of the calculation and also a short matlab code to evaluate the triple cumulant as a function of time in this regime, for any choice of the three points [27].

Appendix B: Numerical results for second cumulants. To obtain the Lagrangian Monte Carlo results for the three-point skewness \mathcal{S}_{123} plotted in Fig. 2, not only are the results required for the triple cumulant C_{123} plotted in Fig. 1 but also required are the second cumulants C_{13} , C_{23} , C_{12} . The results for the second cumulant from the same Lagrangian Monte Carlo scheme were presented in our earlier paper [25] and these were compared there with the large-separation, short-time approximation (4). However, for completeness, we present here a similar comparison for the particular combination $(C_{13} C_{23} C_{12})^{1/2}$ that appears in our definition of the three-point skewness. In Fig. 4, we show this combination for the same three points and for the same τ values as that for the triple cumulants plotted in Fig. 1. An interesting observation is that the Monte Carlo errors are much smaller for the

FIG. 4. Combined second cumulants $(C_{13}C_{23}C_{12})^{1/2}$ for the vertical equilateral triangle with side lengths $r^* = 50$ and for initial mean concentration profiles with $\tau^* = 10^4, 10^6, 10^8,$ and 10^{10} going from left to right, top to bottom, respectively. Solid lines with symbols and shades represent numerical results and dashed lines the analytical prediction. Monte Carlo error is too small to be visible at this scale.

second cumulants than for the triple cumulants. In fact, it is these small error bars that, by standard propagation of error formulas, led to the relative smaller errors in the three-point skewness in Fig. 2 relative to the triple cumulant in Fig. 1. We have also plotted in Fig. 4 the predictions of the large-separation, short-time asymptotics. It can be seen especially in the insets of the figures, which enlarge into the short-time region, that the agreement between the analytical and numerical results is excellent. This close agreement provides a good check on both methods.

Appendix C: One-point PDFs of concentration fluctuations. Although it is not immediately obvious how to calculate the PDF of concentration fluctuations at multiple space points, it is easy in our model for $D_0 = 0$ to evaluate the PDF at a single point by using the fact that $c(\mathbf{x}, t) = c_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}(t))$, where $\boldsymbol{\xi}(0) = \mathbf{x}$ and $d\boldsymbol{\xi}/dt = \mathbf{w}$ is a white-noise process with covariance $\langle w_i(t)w_j(t') \rangle = 2D\delta_{ij}\delta(t-t')$. Since our nondimensionalization corresponds to taking $2D = 1$, this gives $c^*(z^*, t^*) = c_0^*(z^* + \sqrt{t^*}N)$ in dimensionless variables, with N a standard normal random variable. From our adopted initial concentration profile $c_0^*(\zeta^*) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \text{erf}(\frac{\zeta^*}{\sqrt{2\tau^*}}))$, it is then straightforward to find the PDF of the concentration $c^*(z^*, t^*)$.

Because $c_0^*(\zeta^*)$ is a nonlinear function, this random variable is in general non-normal. For example, when $t^* = \tau^*$,

the theory of inverse transform sampling implies that $c^*(0, t^*)$ has a uniform distribution on the unit interval $[0, 1]$ of concentration values and for increasing $t^* > \tau^*$ its PDF becomes more peaked at values $c^* = 0$ and $c^* = 1$. On the other hand, in the opposite limit of weak concentration gradients, $\tau^* \gg t^*$, $(z^*)^2/2$, the result

$$c_0^*(\zeta^*) \simeq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{2}{\pi \tau^*} \right)^{1/2} \zeta^* \right)$$

implies that

$$c^*(z^*, t^*) \simeq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{2t^*}{\pi \tau^*} \right)^{1/2} N \right)$$

and converges to a Gaussian random variable with mean $\frac{1}{2}$ and standard deviation $\propto \nabla c_0^*$. It should be noted that a similar result holds also for $D_0 > 0$, since this amounts simply to replacing $D \mapsto D + D_0$.

Thus, the single-point statistics of the concentration indeed become Gaussian in the limit $\nabla c_0 \rightarrow 0$. This fact underlines the nontriviality of our results for multipoint statistics, which remain non-Gaussian in this same limit.

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Supplemental Material on “Non-Gaussian statistics of concentration fluctuations in free liquid diffusion”

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A. SHORT-TIME, LARGE- r ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTION FOR TRIPLE CUMULANT

We first describe the variables used to represent \mathcal{C}_{123} , in terms of the geometry of the triangle with vertices $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3$. We take as reference the triangle with sides r_{12}, r_{13}, r_{23} and interior angles $\psi_{12}, \psi_{13}, \psi_{23}$ located in the first quadrant of the xy -plane with vertex 3 at the origin and side \mathbf{r}_{13} along the x -axis. See Figure 1. Applying rotation $R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = R_z(\alpha)R_x(\beta)R_z(\gamma)$ around point 3 and then translating point 3 by (X, Y, Z) , the general position and orientation of the triangle as a rigid body in space is specified by 9 variables: 3 side-lengths r_{12}, r_{13}, r_{23} , 3 Euler angles α, β, γ , and 3 coordinates (X, Y, Z) of vertex 3. The number of independent variables is reduced from 9 to 6 by using translational symmetry along the planar interface (eliminating X, Y) and rotational symmetry around the gradient direction (eliminating α). Transforming Cartesian variables $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3$ to these new variables, therefore, the 3rd order cumulant \mathcal{C}_{123} can be written entirely in terms of $r_{12}, r_{23}, r_{13}, \beta, \gamma, Z$. The shape variables are subject to the triangle inequalities $r_{pq} \leq r_{ik} + r_{jk}$ for i, j, k any cyclic permutation of 1, 2, 3. It is thus more convenient to use unconstrained variables $r_{13}, r_{23}, \psi_{12}$ to specify triangle shape and recover the others from the trigonometric laws of cosines and sines:

$$r_{12} = (r_{13}^2 + r_{23}^2 - 2r_{13}r_{23} \cos(\psi_{12}))^{1/2}; \quad \psi_{23} = \arcsin(r_{23} \sin(\psi_{12})/r_{12}); \quad \psi_{13} = \arcsin(r_{13} \sin(\psi_{12})/r_{12}) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Triangle orientation is specified by rotating coordinate vectors $\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}, \hat{\mathbf{z}}$, by $R_x(\beta)R_z(\gamma)$ into a new orthogonal system

$$\mathbf{l} = (\cos \gamma, \cos \beta \sin \gamma, \sin \beta \sin \gamma)^\top; \quad \mathbf{m} = (-\sin \gamma, \cos \beta \cos \gamma, \sin \beta \cos \gamma)^\top; \quad \mathbf{n} = (0, -\sin \beta, \cos \beta)^\top, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

which then gives the triangle side vectors $\mathbf{r}_{13}, \mathbf{r}_{23}, \mathbf{r}_{12}$, in general position:

$$\mathbf{r}_{13} = r_{13}\mathbf{l}; \quad \mathbf{r}_{23} = r_{23}(\cos \psi_{12}\mathbf{l} + \sin \psi_{12}\mathbf{m}); \quad \mathbf{r}_{12} = r_{12}(\cos \psi_{23}\mathbf{l} - \sin \psi_{23}\mathbf{m}). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

FIG. 1 Illustration of the triangle formed by vertices $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3$, in reference position in the horizontal plane.

The variables used to represent the second cumulant \mathcal{C}_{pq} for the two points $\mathbf{x}_p, \mathbf{x}_q$ are the radial distance r_{pq} , the polar angle θ_{pq} , and the mean height $Z_{pq} = \frac{1}{2}(z_p + z_q)$. The forcing terms in equation (4) of the Main Text for \mathcal{C}_{123} involve the gradients of the second cumulants and thus we must relate its variables to those that we have adopted for \mathcal{C}_{123} . The z -coordinates of the triangle side vectors can be represented also by the polar angles relative to vector $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$

$$z_{13} = r_{13} \cos \theta_{13}; \quad z_{23} = r_{23} \cos \theta_{23}; \quad z_{12} = r_{12} \cos \theta_{12}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

so that comparing with equation (A.3) yields:

$$\cos \theta_{13} = \sin \beta \sin \gamma; \quad \cos \theta_{23} = \sin \beta \sin(\gamma + \psi_{12}); \quad \cos \theta_{12} = \sin \beta \sin(\gamma - \psi_{23}); \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Recalling $Z = z_3$, the mean vertical heights of the triangle legs are then given by

$$Z_{13} = Z + \frac{1}{2}z_{13}; \quad Z_{23} = Z + \frac{1}{2}z_{23}; \quad Z_{12} = Z + \frac{1}{2}(z_{13} + z_{23}) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

The six forcing or source terms that appear on the right side of equation (4) of the Main Text for \mathcal{C}_{123} can be obtained by straightforward but lengthy computations. We give only the final results:

$$F_{123} = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r_{12}} \bar{c}'(z_1) \left\{ (\cos \theta_{23} - \cos \psi_{13} \cos \theta_{12}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{23}}{\partial r_{23}} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta_{23} + \cos \theta_{12} (\cos \theta_{12} + \cos \psi_{13} \cos \theta_{23})}{r_{23}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{23}}{\partial (\cos \theta_{23})} + \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{12}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{23}}{\partial Z_{23}} \right\} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$F_{213} = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r_{12}} \bar{c}'(z_2) \left\{ (\cos \theta_{13} + \cos \psi_{23} \cos \theta_{12}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{13}}{\partial r_{13}} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta_{13} + \cos \theta_{12} (\cos \theta_{12} - \cos \psi_{23} \cos \theta_{13})}{r_{13}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{13}}{\partial (\cos \theta_{13})} + \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{12}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{13}}{\partial Z_{13}} \right\} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$F_{132} = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r_{13}} \bar{c}'(z_1) \left\{ -(\cos \theta_{23} + \cos \psi_{12} \cos \theta_{13}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{23}}{\partial r_{23}} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta_{23} + \cos \theta_{13} (\cos \theta_{13} - \cos \psi_{12} \cos \theta_{23})}{r_{23}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{23}}{\partial (\cos \theta_{23})} + \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{13}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{23}}{\partial Z_{23}} \right\} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$F_{312} = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r_{12}} \bar{c}'(z_3) \left\{ (\cos \theta_{12} + \cos \psi_{23} \cos \theta_{13}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{12}}{\partial r_{12}} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta_{12} + \cos \theta_{13} (\cos \theta_{13} - \cos \psi_{23} \cos \theta_{23})}{r_{12}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{12}}{\partial (\cos \theta_{12})} + \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{13}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{12}}{\partial Z_{12}} \right\} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$F_{231} = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r_{23}} \bar{c}'(z_2) \left\{ -(\cos \theta_{13} + \cos \psi_{12} \cos \theta_{23}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{13}}{\partial r_{13}} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta_{13} + \cos \theta_{23} (\cos \theta_{23} - \cos \psi_{12} \cos \theta_{13})}{r_{13}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{13}}{\partial (\cos \theta_{13})} + \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{23}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{13}}{\partial Z_{13}} \right\} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$F_{321} = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r_{23}} \bar{c}'(z_3) \left\{ (-\cos \theta_{12} + \cos \psi_{13} \cos \theta_{23}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{12}}{\partial r_{12}} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta_{12} + \cos \theta_{23} (\cos \theta_{23} + \cos \psi_{13} \cos \theta_{12})}{r_{12}} \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{12}}{\partial (\cos \theta_{12})} + \frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{23}) \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{12}}{\partial Z_{12}} \right\} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

In order to calculate the leading-order asymptotic approximation to \mathcal{C}_{123} for short times and large- r , we must substitute into the forcing terms the corresponding derivatives of the mean, $\nabla\bar{c}(z, t) = c_0 \exp(-z^2/4D(t+\tau))/\sqrt{4\pi D(t+\tau)}$, and of the second cumulants. The latter are obtained from equation (6) in the Main Text to be

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{pq}}{\partial r_{pq}} = -\frac{\mathcal{C}_{pq}}{r_{pq}} - \frac{3c_0^2}{16\pi} \frac{\sigma}{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{pq}) \cos^2 \theta_{pq} \left\{ \exp\left(-\frac{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2}{2D(t+\tau)}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2}{2D\tau}\right) \right\} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{pq}}{\partial(\cos \theta_{pq})} = -\frac{2 \cos \theta_{pq}}{1 + \cos^2 \theta_{pq}} \mathcal{C}_{pq} - \frac{3c_0^2}{16\pi} \frac{\sigma r_{pq}}{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{pq}) \cos \theta_{pq} \left\{ \exp\left(-\frac{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2}{2D(t+\tau)}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2}{2D\tau}\right) \right\} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{C}_{pq}}{\partial Z_{pq}} = -\frac{3c_0^2}{4\pi} \frac{\sigma}{r_{pq}} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{pq}) \frac{Z_{pq}}{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2} \left\{ \exp\left(-\frac{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2}{2D(t+\tau)}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{Z_{pq}^2 + \frac{1}{4}z_{pq}^2}{2D\tau}\right) \right\} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Finally, we must integrate in time the six forcing terms and sum them to obtain the asymptotic result for \mathcal{C}_{123} . The time-integration of the products of the mean gradient and of the derivatives of the second cumulants in (A.13)-(A.15) leads, in addition to elementary integrals, also to two less trivial integrals. The first can be evaluated by the change of variables $u = 1/(s + \tau)$ as follows

$$\int_0^t \frac{e^{-c/(s+\tau)}}{\sqrt{s+\tau}} ds = c^{1/2} \left[\Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{c}{t+\tau}\right) - \Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{c}{\tau}\right) \right] \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where $\Gamma(\alpha, z)$ is the incomplete Gamma function [1, (8.2.2)]. Thus, one gets the first integral

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^t \frac{e^{-a/(s+\tau)}}{\sqrt{s+\tau}} \left[e^{-b/(s+\tau)} - e^{-b/\tau} \right] ds \\ &= (a+b)^{1/2} \left[\Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{a+b}{t+\tau}\right) - \Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{a+b}{\tau}\right) \right] - a^{1/2} e^{-\frac{b}{\tau}} \left[\Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{a}{t+\tau}\right) - \Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{a}{\tau}\right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

By using the expression for the incomplete Gamma function in terms of the Kummer confluent hypergeometric function U [1, (8.5.3)]:

$$\Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}, z\right) = e^{-z} U\left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2}; z\right), \quad (\text{A.18})$$

one thus gets also

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^t \frac{e^{-a/(s+\tau)}}{\sqrt{s+\tau}} \left[e^{-b/(s+\tau)} - e^{-b/\tau} \right] ds \\ &= (a+b)^{1/2} \left[e^{-\frac{a+b}{t+\tau}} U\left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a+b}{t+\tau}\right) - e^{-\frac{a+b}{\tau}} U\left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a+b}{\tau}\right) \right] - a^{1/2} e^{-\frac{b}{\tau}} \left[e^{-\frac{a}{t+\tau}} U\left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a}{t+\tau}\right) - e^{-\frac{a}{\tau}} U\left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2}; \frac{a}{\tau}\right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

The second time integral that appears is

$$I_2 = \int_0^t \frac{e^{-a/(s+\tau)}}{\sqrt{s+\tau}} \left[E_1\left(\frac{b}{s+\tau}\right) - E_1\left(\frac{b}{\tau}\right) \right] ds \quad (\text{A.20})$$

and we have found no exact analytical expression for it. Instead we shall evaluate I_2 by numerical quadrature.

For short times t , the analytical results (A.17),(A.19) for I_1 and the integrand in the definition (A.20) of I_2 are all subject to cancellations from subtracting nearly equal terms. In that case we can obtain analytical results from series expansion. For I_1 we can use the series representation of the incomplete Gamma function [1, (8.7.3)] and the binomial expansion to obtain

$$c^\alpha \left[\Gamma\left(-\alpha, \frac{c}{t+\tau}\right) - \Gamma\left(-\alpha, \frac{c}{\tau}\right) \right] = \tau^\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n!} \left(\frac{c}{\tau}\right)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k-1} \frac{(n-\alpha+1)^{k+1}}{k!} \left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right)^k$$

(A.21)

We apply this for $\alpha = 1/2$ with $c = a + b$, a . For the integrand of I_2 we use [1, (6.6.2)] to obtain

$$E_1\left(\frac{b}{s+\tau}\right) - E_1\left(\frac{b}{\tau}\right) = \ln\left(1 + \frac{s}{\tau}\right) - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{-b}{s+\tau}\right)^k \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{j!(k-j)!} \left(\frac{s}{\tau}\right)^j \quad (\text{A.22})$$

When $\frac{a+b}{\tau}$ is sufficiently large, above some threshold Θ , then the expression (A.19) for I_1 is accurate. In our numerical work, we took $\Theta = 10$. However, for $\frac{a+b}{\tau} < \Theta$ we must use the expansion (A.21) for $\alpha = 1/2$ with $c = a + b$, a . There is still a difficulty, because the factor $(a+b)^n - a^n e^{-b/\tau}$ in the double summation is subject to loss of significance error when b is small. Thus, we rewrite this term as

$$(a+b)^n - a^n e^{-b/\tau} = 2a^n e^{-b/2\tau} \sinh\left(\frac{b}{2\tau}\right) + \sum_{m=1}^n \binom{n}{m} a^{n-m} b^m \quad (\text{A.23})$$

to avoid the cancellation of significant digits. For $\frac{b}{\tau}$ sufficiently large, above some threshold Θ , then the expression for I_2 in (A.20) for the integrand is accurate. We took $\Theta = 1$. Otherwise, we define the integral by the expansion (A.22). In either case, the time-integral I_2 is evaluated using the 2nd-order composite trapezoid rule. A script in `Matlab` is appended below, which carries out all of the numerical evaluations discussed above.

Finally, we note that great simplifications occur in the large- τ limit. To leader-order accuracy, only terms $\propto t/\tau$ need be retained in the summations (A.21)-(A.22). Note, in particular, that the mean concentration gradient becomes t -independent to leading order: $\nabla \bar{c} \sim \nabla c_0 \sim c_0/\sqrt{4\pi D\tau}$. The time-integrals of the forcing terms thus simplify and reduce to time-integrals of only the derivatives of the second cumulants. These are easily evaluated for large- τ to be

$$\int_0^t \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}}{\partial r_{pq}}(r_{pq}, \cos \theta_{pq}, Z_{pq}, s) ds \sim -\frac{3}{4} |\nabla c_0|^2 \frac{\sigma}{r_{pq}^2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{pq}) Dt^2 \quad (\text{A.24})$$

$$\int_0^t \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}}{\partial (\cos \theta_{pq})}(r_{pq}, \cos \theta_{pq}, Z_{pq}, s) ds \sim \frac{3}{2} |\nabla c_0|^2 \frac{\sigma}{r_{pq}} \cos \theta_{pq} Dt^2 \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$\int_0^t \frac{\partial \mathcal{C}}{\partial Z_{pq}}(r_{pq}, \cos \theta_{pq}, Z_{pq}, s) ds \sim -3\pi |\nabla c_0|^4 \frac{\sigma}{r_{pq}} (1 + \cos^2 \theta_{pq}) Z_{pq} \frac{Dt^2}{c_0^2} \quad (\text{A.26})$$

The latter derivative is thus sub-leading compared with the other two and may be neglected.

To give some intuition about the complex formulas, we plot in Figure 2 the three-point skewness, $\mathcal{S}_{123} = \mathcal{C}_{123}/(\mathcal{C}_{12}\mathcal{C}_{13}\mathcal{C}_{23})^{1/2}$ in the limit of vanishing mean concentration gradient, for varying orientation of the triangle (left panel) and for varying triangle shape (right panel). It is notable that the configuration studied in the main text does not have maximum possible skewness.

FIG. 2 Dependence of the asymptotic three-point skewness, $\mathcal{S}_{123} = \mathcal{C}_{123}/(\mathcal{C}_{12}\mathcal{C}_{13}\mathcal{C}_{23})^{1/2}$, on triangle orientation (specified by Euler angles, β and γ) and on triangle shape (specified by internal angles, ψ_{12} and ψ_{13} , subject to the restriction $0 \leq \psi_{13} + \psi_{12} \leq \pi$). In the *left* panel the triangle is equilateral with side lengths $r^* = 50$, while the *right* panel refers to a vertical triangle, $\beta = \pi/2$ and $\gamma = 0$, with arithmetic mean of side lengths = 50. All data refer to $t^* = 100$ and red dots represent the configuration studied in the Main Text.

```

1  clear all
2
3  % INPUTS
4
5  % geometry
6
7  r13=1e4;
8  r23=1e4;
9  ps12=3*pi/2;
10
11 % orientation
12
13 % alp=0, gam from 0 to 2*pi, bet from 0 to pi
14 alp=0;
15 bet=pi/2;
16 gam=pi/3;
17
18 % vertical location
19 z3=-5e3;
20
21 % time interval and time step
22
23 T=1;
24 dt=0.005;
25 t=0:dt:T;
26
27 % gradient parameter
28
29 tau=1e13;
30
31
32 % OUTPUTS
33
34 % derived quantities for triangle
35
36 r12=sqrt(r13^2+r23^2-2*r13*r23*cos(ps12));
37 ps23=asin(r23*sin(ps12)/r12);
38 ps13=asin(r13*sin(ps12)/r12);
39
40 costh13=sin(bet)*sin(gam);
41 costh23=sin(bet)*sin(gam+ps12);
42 costh12=sin(bet)*sin(gam-ps23);
43
44
45 lh=[cos(alp)*cos(gam)-sin(alp)*cos(bet)*sin(gam); ...
46     sin(alp)*cos(gam)+cos(alp)*cos(bet)*sin(gam); ...
47     sin(bet)*sin(gam)];
48
49 mh=[-cos(alp)*sin(gam)-sin(alp)*cos(bet)*cos(gam); ...
50     -sin(alp)*sin(gam)+cos(alp)*cos(bet)*cos(gam); ...
51     sin(bet)*cos(gam)];
52
53 nh=[sin(bet)*sin(alp); -sin(bet)*cos(alp); cos(bet)];
54
55 rv13=r13*lh;
56 rv23=r23*(cos(ps12)*lh+sin(ps12)*mh);
57 rv12=r12*(cos(ps23)*lh-sin(ps23)*mh);
58
59 z1=z3+rv13(3); z2=z3+rv23(3);
60 Z12=(z1+z2)/2; Z23=(z2+z3)/2; Z13=(z1+z3)/2;
61
62 % FIRST MOMENTS
63
64 C1=meanf(z1,tau,t);
65 C2=meanf(z2,tau,t);
66 C3=meanf(z3,tau,t);
67
68 % SECOND MOMENTS
69

```

```

70 C13=covf(r13, cosh13, Z13, tau, t);
71 C23=covf(r23, cosh23, Z23, tau, t);
72 C12=covf(r12, cosh12, Z12, tau, t);
73
74 % THIRD MOMENT
75
76 btaumax=0;
77
78
79 % source term 123
80 A=cosh23-cos(ps13)*cosh12;
81 B=(1-cosh23^2+cosh12*(cosh12+cos(ps13)*cosh23))/r23;
82 C=(1+cosh12^2)/2;
83
84 a=z1^2/2;
85 z23=r23*cosh23;
86 b=Z23^2+z23^2/4; btaumax=max(b/tau, btaumax);
87 I1=int1(a, b, tau, t);
88 I2=int2(a, b, tau, dt, T);
89
90 dC123=-A*(3*(1+cosh23^2)/r23^2/8/pi)*I2;
91 dC123= dC123 -A*(3*(1+cosh23^2)*cosh23^2/b/16/pi)*I1;
92 dC123= dC123 + B*(3*cosh23/r23/4/pi)*I2;
93 dC123= dC123 - B*(3*r23*(1+cosh23^2)*cosh23/b/16/pi)*I1;
94 dC123= dC123 -C*(3*(1+cosh23^2)*Z23/b/r23/4/pi)*I1;
95 dC123=dC123/r12;
96
97 C123=dC123;
98
99 % source term 213
100 A=cosh13+cos(ps23)*cosh12;
101 B=(1-cosh13^2+cosh12*(cosh12-cos(ps23)*cosh13))/r13;
102 C=(1+cosh12^2)/2;
103
104 a=z2^2/2;
105 z13=r13*cosh13;
106 b=Z13^2+z13^2/4; btaumax=max(b/tau, btaumax);
107 I1=int1(a, b, tau, t);
108 I2=int2(a, b, tau, dt, T);
109
110 dC123=-A*(3*(1+cosh13^2)/r13^2/8/pi)*I2;
111 dC123= dC123 -A*(3*(1+cosh13^2)*cosh13^2/b/16/pi)*I1;
112 dC123= dC123 + B*(3*cosh13/r13/4/pi)*I2;
113 dC123= dC123 - B*(3*r13*(1+cosh13^2)*cosh13/b/16/pi)*I1;
114 dC123= dC123 -C*(3*(1+cosh13^2)*Z13/b/r13/4/pi)*I1;
115 dC123=dC123/r12;
116
117 C123=C123+dC123;
118
119 % source term 132
120 A=- (cosh23+cos(ps12)*cosh13);
121 B=- (1-cosh23^2+cosh13*(cosh13-cos(ps12)*cosh23))/r23;
122 C=(1+cosh13^2)/2;
123
124 a=z1^2/2;
125 z23=r23*cosh23;
126 b=Z23^2+z23^2/4; btaumax=max(b/tau, btaumax);
127 I1=int1(a, b, tau, t);
128 I2=int2(a, b, tau, dt, T);
129
130 dC123=-A*(3*(1+cosh23^2)/r23^2/8/pi)*I2;
131 dC123= dC123 -A*(3*(1+cosh23^2)*cosh23^2/b/16/pi)*I1;
132 dC123= dC123 + B*(3*cosh23/r23/4/pi)*I2;
133 dC123= dC123 - B*(3*r23*(1+cosh23^2)*cosh23/b/16/pi)*I1;
134 dC123= dC123 -C*(3*(1+cosh23^2)*Z23/b/r23/4/pi)*I1;
135 dC123=dC123/r13;
136
137 C123=C123+dC123;
138
139 % source term 312

```

```

140 A=cosh12+cos(ps23)*cosh13;
141 B=(1-cosh12^2+cosh13*(cosh13-cos(ps23)*cosh23))/r12;
142 C=(1+cosh13^2)/2;
143
144 a=z3^2/2;
145 z12=r12*cosh12;
146 b=z12^2+z12^2/4; btaumax=max(b/tau,btaumax);
147 I1=int1(a,b,tau,t);
148 I2=int2(a,b,tau,dt,T);
149
150 dC123=-A*(3*(1+cosh12^2)/r12^2/8/pi)*I2;
151 dC123= dC123 -A*(3*(1+cosh12^2)*cosh12^2/b/16/pi)*I1;
152 dC123= dC123 + B*(3*cosh12/r12/4/pi)*I2;
153 dC123= dC123 - B*(3*r12*(1+cosh12^2)*cosh12/b/16/pi)*I1;
154 dC123= dC123 -C*(3*(1+cosh12^2)*z12/b/r12/4/pi)*I1;
155 dC123=dC123/r13;
156
157 C123=C123+dC123;
158
159 % source term 231
160 A=-(cosh13+cos(ps12)*cosh23);
161 B=-(1-cosh13^2+cosh23*(cosh23-cos(ps12)*cosh13))/r13;
162 C=(1+cosh23^2)/2;
163
164 a=z2^2/2;
165 z13=r13*cosh13;
166 b=z13^2+z13^2/4; btaumax=max(b/tau,btaumax);
167 I1=int1(a,b,tau,t);
168 I2=int2(a,b,tau,dt,T);
169
170 dC123=-A*(3*(1+cosh13^2)/r13^2/8/pi)*I2;
171 dC123= dC123 -A*(3*(1+cosh13^2)*cosh13^2/b/16/pi)*I1;
172 dC123= dC123 + B*(3*cosh13/r13/4/pi)*I2;
173 dC123= dC123 - B*(3*r13*(1+cosh13^2)*cosh13/b/16/pi)*I1;
174 dC123= dC123 -C*(3*(1+cosh13^2)*z13/b/r13/4/pi)*I1;
175 dC123=dC123/r23;
176
177 C123=C123+dC123;
178
179 % source term 321
180 A=-cosh12+cos(ps13)*cosh23;
181 B=-(1-cosh12^2+cosh23*(cosh23+cos(ps13)*cosh12))/r12;
182 C=(1+cosh23^2)/2;
183
184 a=z3^2/2;
185 z12=r12*cosh12;
186 b=z12^2+z12^2/4; btaumax=max(b/tau,btaumax);
187 I1=int1(a,b,tau,t);
188 I2=int2(a,b,tau,dt,T);
189
190 dC123=-A*(3*(1+cosh12^2)/r12^2/8/pi)*I2;
191 dC123= dC123 -A*(3*(1+cosh12^2)*cosh12^2/b/16/pi)*I1;
192 dC123= dC123 + B*(3*cosh12/r12/4/pi)*I2;
193 dC123= dC123 - B*(3*r12*(1+cosh12^2)*cosh12/b/16/pi)*I1;
194 dC123= dC123 -C*(3*(1+cosh12^2)*z12/b/r12/4/pi)*I1;
195 dC123=dC123/r23;
196
197 C123=C123+dC123;
198
199
200 C123=C123*.75/sqrt(2*pi);
201
202 figure
203 plot(t,C123)
204 title('triple cumulant')
205
206 figure
207 N123=C123./sqrt(abs(C13.*C23.*C12));
208 plot(t,N123)
209 title('normalized triple cumulant')

```

```

210
211 btaumax=btaumax
212
213
214 function y=int1(a,b,tau,t)
215
216 if a+b≤10*tau
217
218 y=zeros(size(t));
219 nn=0;
220 next=ones(size(t));
221 fac=1;
222 while norm(next,'inf')>eps*norm(y,'inf')
223 next=t/tau;
224 dnext=next;
225 kk=2;
226 while norm(dnext,'inf')>eps*norm(next,'inf')
227 dnext=-(nn+kk-1.5)*dnext.*(t/tau)/kk;
228 next=next+dnext;
229 kk=kk+1;
230 end
231 mult=a^nn+2*exp(-b/tau/2)*sinh(b/tau/2);
232 if nn≥1
233 for mm=1:nn
234 mult=mult+nchoosek(nn,mm)*a^(nn-mm)*b^mm;
235 end
236 end
237 next=fac*next*mult;
238 y=y+next;
239 nn=nn+1;
240 fac=-fac/nn/tau;
241 end
242 y=sqrt(tau)*y;
243
244 else
245 y=sqrt(a+b)*(exp(-(a+b)/(t+tau)).*kummerU(1.5,1.5,(a+b)/(t+tau))...
246 -exp(-(a+b)/tau)*kummerU(1.5,1.5,(a+b)/tau));
247 y=y-sqrt(a)*exp(-b/tau)*(exp(-a/(t+tau)).*kummerU(1.5,1.5,a/(t+tau))...
248 -exp(-a/tau)*kummerU(1.5,1.5,a/tau));
249 end
250
251 end
252
253 function y=int2(a,b,tau,dt,tf)
254
255 s=0:dt:tf;
256
257 if b≤5*tau
258 diff=log(1+s/tau);
259 next=1;
260 kk=1;
261 while norm(next,'inf')>eps*norm(diff,'inf')
262 jj=1:kk;
263 S=ones(kk,1)*s;
264 JJ=jj.*ones(size(s));
265 nsum=sum((S/tau).^JJ./factorial(JJ)./factorial(kk-JJ),1);
266 next=nsum.*(-b./(s+tau)).^kk/kk;
267 diff=diff-next;
268 kk=kk+1;
269 end
270 f=exp(-a./(s+tau)).*diff./sqrt(s+tau);
271
272 else
273 f=exp(-a./(s+tau)).*(expint(b./(s+tau))-expint(b/tau))./sqrt(s+tau);
274 end
275 y=cumtrapz(s,f);
276
277 end
278
279 function y=meanf(z,tau,t)

```

```
280
281 y=(1+erf(z./sqrt(2*(t+tau)))/2;
282
283 end
284
285 function y=covf(r,costh,Z,tau,t)
286
287 z=r*costh;
288 b=Z^2+z^2/4;
289
290 if b<= tau
291 diff=log(1+t/tau);
292 next=ones(size(t));
293 kk=1;
294 while norm(next,'inf')>eps*norm(diff,'inf')
295 jj=1:kk;
296 T=ones(kk,1)*t;
297 JJ=jj.'*ones(size(t));
298 nsum=sum((T/tau).^JJ./factorial(JJ)./factorial(kk-JJ),1);
299 next=nsum.*(-b./(t+tau)).^kk/kk;
300 diff=diff-next;
301 kk=kk+1;
302 end
303 y=3*(1+costh^2)*diff/r/(8*pi);
304
305 else
306 y=3*(1+costh^2)*(expint(b./(t+tau))-expint(b/tau))/r/(8*pi);
307 end
308
309 end
```

B. LAGRANGIAN MONTE CARLO NUMERICAL METHOD AND HPC IMPLEMENTATION

We exploit a Lagrangian numerical scheme that was developed to calculate statistical correlation functions of a passive scalar advected by the Kraichnan model of a turbulent velocity field [2–4]. To calculate the P th moment function of the concentration field $\langle c(\mathbf{x}_1, t) \cdots c(\mathbf{x}_P, t) \rangle$, the DFV model is first solved for $c(\mathbf{x}_p, t)$ at the points \mathbf{x}_p , $p = 1, \dots, P$ in one realization of the thermal velocity \mathbf{w} . This is accomplished by setting $c(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_p(t))$ where $d\boldsymbol{\xi}_p/dt = \mathbf{w}_p$, $\boldsymbol{\xi}_p(0) = \mathbf{x}_p$, $p = 1, \dots, P$ with $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{W}} = (\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_P)$ a $3P$ -dimensional Gaussian white-noise with covariance

$$\langle w_{pi}(t)w_{qj}(t') \rangle_{\Xi} = R_{pq}(\boldsymbol{\xi}_p(t), \boldsymbol{\xi}_q(t))\delta(t - t'), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

for fixed $\Xi = (\boldsymbol{\xi}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\xi}_P)$ and for $p, q = 1, \dots, P$ and $i, j = 1, \dots, d$ in space dimension d . The evolution of the P stochastic Lagrangian tracers, $\boldsymbol{\xi}_p(t)$, $p = 1, \dots, P$ is implemented with an Euler-Maruyama discretization

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_p(t + \Delta t) = \boldsymbol{\xi}_p(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_p\sqrt{\Delta t}, \quad p = 1, \dots, P, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_P = (\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_1, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_P)$ is a normal random variable having mean zero and $Pd \times Pd$ covariance matrix

$$R_{pi,qj} = R_{pq}(\boldsymbol{\xi}_p(t), \boldsymbol{\xi}_q(t)), \quad (\text{B.3})$$

for $p, q = 1, \dots, P$ and $i, j = 1, \dots, d$ in d space dimensions. We can generate an independent sample of the Pd -random vector by writing it as $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_P = \mathbf{L}_P\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_P$, where \mathbf{L}_P is the lower triangular Cholesky factor of the positive-definite covariance matrix (B.3) and $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_P$ is a Pd -dimensional standard normal vector. Since our focus is on the triple cumulant, we thus take $P = 3$ and evolve a triplet $\Xi = (\boldsymbol{\xi}_1, \boldsymbol{\xi}_2, \boldsymbol{\xi}_3)$ of stochastic Lagrangian tracers in each realization \mathbf{w} of the thermal velocity field, obtaining thereby $c(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_p(t))$ for $p = 1, 2, 3$.

As in the earlier work on turbulent advection [2–4], the ensemble average that defines the triple cumulant is then approximated by an empirical average

$$C(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3, t) \simeq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_1, t)c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_2, t)c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_3, t) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

over a large number N of independent samples, where the concentration fluctuation field is defined by $c^{(n)}(\mathbf{x}_p, t) = c_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_p^{(n)}(t)) - \bar{c}(\mathbf{x}_p, t)$ and $\boldsymbol{\xi}_p^{(n)}(t)$, $n = 1, \dots, N$ are independent solutions of (B.2). The convergence of the sample average (B.4) as $N \rightarrow \infty$ is slow, with typical Monte Carlo errors $\propto 1/\sqrt{N}$. Nevertheless, the scheme yielded accurate results for turbulent advection [2–4] with a number of samples at most $N \sim 10^7$. Unfortunately, our problem differs in two crucial respects. First, the covariance for the Kraichnan model of a turbulent velocity field had covariance increasing with r , whereas the velocity corresponding to thermal noise has covariance proportional to the Oseen tensor

$$R_{ij}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{k_B T}{4\pi\eta r}(\delta_{ij} + \hat{r}_i\hat{r}_j), \quad r \gtrsim \sigma \quad (\text{B.5})$$

and thus decreasing with r . The consequence is that the elements in the $Pd \times Pd$ matrix (B.3) off-diagonal in p, q , which are entirely responsible for producing correlations between particles, grow smaller in time for our problem as particles separate. The second key difference is that the turbulence studies [2–4] considered a statistical steady-state for the passive scalar with large-scale injection, whereas we study the problem of free diffusion for which the concentration correlations decay in time. This decaying magnitude makes it more difficult to achieve acceptable relative error. Both of these differences require that N must be very much larger in our problem. Fortunately, the calculation of the sample average (B.4) is trivially parallelizable, with only the requirement to choose independent seeds for pseudorandom number generators on different processors.

We have developed and implemented a Monte Carlo algorithm based on a regularized version of (B.5) that accounts for the filtering of wavenumbers $\gtrsim 1/\sigma$. Specifically, we implement the exponentially decaying kernel proposed in [5], Appendix D, that also reproduces the expected Stokes-Einstein macroscopic diffusivity $D = k_B T/6\pi\eta\sigma$. For the sake of better performance, the numerical solver implements the regularization from [5] in (B.3) when $r_{pq} := |\boldsymbol{\xi}_p - \boldsymbol{\xi}_q| \leq 10\sigma$ and employs (B.5) otherwise. Moreover, we exploit an adaptive time-stepping method for the Euler-Maruyama time-discretization in (B.2) such that $\Delta t = f\rho^2/2D$, where $\rho = \min_{p,q} |\boldsymbol{\xi}_p - \boldsymbol{\xi}_q|$ and $0 < f \leq 1$ is a parameter controlling what fraction of the distance between the nearest two Lagrangian tracers can be covered on average with one time-step. We use $f = 0.2$ in our results – tests with smaller and larger fractions confirm the time-scheme is converging. In addition, the results of the Main Text related to the long-time behavior are obtained imposing a minimum of 10 time-steps between consecutive data points to ensure smooth plots.

FIG. 3 Scheme illustrating the parallelization strategy and data management. Very large samples of realizations are independently run by several MPI processes and GPU devices each. The final result is obtained through a post-processing.

Although conceptually simple, the Lagrangian Monte Carlo algorithm requires careful implementation to efficiently support an extremely high number of realizations. Given the algorithm’s inherently parallel structure, GPU architectures are the natural choice. To this end, we have developed a CUDA+MPI implementation that minimizes communication – the real bottleneck in reduction-heavy algorithms – by hierarchically distributing realizations and reductions across GPU devices, GPU blocks, warps, and, finally, batches in each thread. Figure 3 shows the parallelization scheme of our GPU code.

In order to manage the enormous number of realizations contributing to the average and to allow running independent Monte Carlo campaigns, we split the computation into smaller samples and compute the overall statistical observables through a post-process. This requires storing some data. Saving the trajectory of each realization for just one of the curves in the Main Text would require ~ 300 PB. We drastically reduce the amount of stored data to ~ 50 MB by saving only the statistically meaningful observables (*i.e.* the cumulants up to third order) at the desired times for very large batches of realizations (called samples in Figure 3). Since each data file now contains the averages over a smaller sample, this data management also allows the central limit theorem to be exploited to compute the Monte Carlo error as the standard deviation of the sample means divided by the square root of the number of samples. This is sensibly faster than computing the standard deviation from each single realization.

Every time the code is launched, it iteratively computes new samples independently. Each sample is distributed over several nodes and GPU devices through standard MPI parallelization. The workload is further distributed over different GPU blocks, each containing several warps of 32 threads. Each thread then runs a batch of 1000 realizations, making the full time evolution of the particles trajectories the innermost loop. In order to compute the desired averages up to the level of samples, many reductions are needed. Proceeding upwards in the scheme of Figure 3, we reduce the partial sums computed by each thread to an intermediate sum over threads of the same warp (this is very efficient). Then, the first thread of each warp inside the same block reduces the sum again exploiting the GPU’s shared memory, therefore no synchronization across blocks is needed up to here. The last reduction inside the GPU device is the `atomicAdd`, which requires blocks to synchronize in order to copy the partial sum to the CPU host. Finally, `MPI_Reduce` is used to collect the partial sums computed by each device and to store the desired averages for each sample at the penultimate level in Figure 3

The CUDA environment also allows using very efficient random number generators. We use `Philox_4x32_10` from the `cuRAND` library with a different seed for each MPI rank (or GPU) generated from the Linux file `/dev/urandom`

and a different state for each thread. Moreover, the `curand_normal12_double` function within the cuRAND library is exploited to halve the cost of producing two random numbers with double precision. Beside managing the large amount of realizations, the implementation of the Monte Carlo algorithm also requires to deal with the loss of significance, typical of averages over very large samples. We mitigate this issue by using double precision and implementing an extended version of the Kahan–Babuška compensated summation provided by Neumaier [6, 7] in all summations and reductions up to the block level. Distributing the summations over many levels of parallelization also helps.

In our computation, the loss of significance is even worsened by the asymptotically decaying concentration profile, $\bar{c}^*(z^*, t^*)$. Indeed, when the particles are outside the interface region, the concentration is almost homogeneous and the small deviations from the asymptotic value might be lost during the evaluation of the concentration fluctuation, $c_0^*(\xi^*) - \bar{c}^*(\mathbf{x}^*, t^*)$. First of all, we shift the profile to be $\in [-0.5, 0.5]$ to balance the number of summations of positive and negative quantities. We use the Heaviside function for $t^* + \tau^* = 0$ and a combination of error function and complementary error function otherwise. In particular, if $z^* \gtrsim \sqrt{2(t^* + \tau^*)}$ or $z^* \lesssim -\sqrt{2(t^* + \tau^*)}$, then $\bar{c}^*(z^*, t^*) = 0.5 - \epsilon$ or $\bar{c}^*(z^*, t^*) = -0.5 + \epsilon$, respectively, with ϵ a small positive deviation. Therefore, we may have loss of significance due to the leading order terms being much larger than the small deviations. To avoid this, we exploit $\operatorname{erf}(z^*) = 1 - \operatorname{erfc}(z^*)$, $\operatorname{erf}(-z^*) = -\operatorname{erf}(z^*)$ in the formula for $\bar{c}^*(z^*, t^*)$, thus separating the leading order term from the remainder ($\epsilon = \frac{1}{2}\operatorname{erfc}|z^*|$). Therefore, the concentration fluctuation is computed by separately subtracting the leading order terms and the remainders, similar to the compensated summations algorithm mentioned above.

Overall, the Monte Carlo code has proven capable to yield up to $N \sim 10^{15}$ independent realizations. Each curve in the insets of Figure 1 and Figure 2 of the Main Text required $\sim 10^{14}$ realizations, whereas those in the main plots (long-time behavior) were obtained with $\sim 3 \times 10^{13}$ realizations. All these data were produced on the Leonardo Tier-0 cluster hosted by CINECA by performing a total of ~ 76 EFLOP in double precision, corresponding to ~ 7700 GPU-hours. Despite the very large computation, the computational cost was as low as ~ 1 GPU-hour per 10^{12} realizations. Indeed, this efficient implementation allowed to reach a performance of 5.8 TFLOP/s per GPU (which is close to the cluster’s peak performance) and run simulations at a rate of ~ 130 TFLOP/s.

C. SUPPLEMENTAL NUMERICAL DATA

We provide here some further numerical data to supplement that presented in the Main Text and End Matter.

Skewness for $r^* = 50$, including $\tau^* = 10^4$

We elected in Fig. 2 of the Main Text to plot numerical results for the three-point skewness only at the three largest values $\tau^* = 10^6, 10^8, 10^{10}$, in order to show better their convergence as $\tau^* \rightarrow \infty$. For completeness, we plot here in Fig. 4 the entire set of results including also $\tau^* = 10^4$. As expected from the sign of the triple cumulant in Fig. 1 of the Main Text for the corresponding value of τ^* , the three-point skewness for $\tau^* = 10^4$ is negative over the entire time range. A simple physical explanation for this sign is lacking and also for its reversal with increasing τ^* . Nevertheless, just as for the other three choices of τ^* , the three-point skewness appears to level off and approach a “quasi-equilibrium” value for $t^* \rightarrow \infty$. An extremely slow decrease to zero might also be suggested by the plotted results and cannot be ruled out. Perhaps the most significant observation from Fig. 4 is that the maximum amplitude of the skewness is two times larger (about 0.02) for $\tau^* = 10^4$ than it is for the higher τ^* values. This has the interesting implication for experiment that sharper interfaces with larger initial concentration gradients may have greater non-Gaussian signatures of the concentration fluctuations. In physical units, taking water at ambient temperature as the reference fluid, the times we have considered in Fig. 4 are only up to 20 ms (as indicated by the labels on the upper abscissa). Nonetheless, taking the mean free path as 2.5 \AA , this value actually corresponds to $\sim 5 \times 10^{10}$ mean free times of the water molecules and is thus quite long on microscopic time scales. Moreover, the mean concentration gradient at the origin at this final time $t^* = 10^4$ when compared with the initial gradient has dropped by the factor 29.3%, 0.496%, 0.005%, $5 \times 10^{-5}\%$ for the four cases $\tau^* = 10^4, 10^6, 10^8, 10^{10}$, respectively. Thus, this time is sufficient to observe macroscopic diffusion of the mean concentration, especially for the sharper interfaces.

Cumulants for $r^* = 100$, short-time regime

In the Main Text and in the End Matter we presented results only for three points forming an equilateral triangle with side-length $r^* = 50$, but comparable results are obtained for other values of r^* and for other triangle shapes and orientations. As representative of this fact, we show here numerical results for an equilateral triangle of the same orientation as the earlier case ($\gamma = 0, \beta = \pi/2$) but instead with $r^* = 100$. These results were computed only for short times $t^* \leq 100$ where they can be directly compared with the asymptotic analytical results derived in SM,§A.

We present first in Figure 5 the results for the three-point skewness with $r^* = 100$, which can be observed to be qualitatively quite similar to those for $r^* = 50$ in Fig. 4. The agreement between numerical Monte Carlo and analytical results is even better than for the smaller r^* , as expected since the asymptotic calculation assumes large r^* and small t^* . The main result of increasing r^* is that the magnitudes of the three-point skewness have become smaller, in agreement with analytical predictions.

The input results for calculating the skewness at $r^* = 100$ are presented in the remaining plots, Figure 6 for the triple cumulant \mathcal{C}_{123} and Figure 7 for the combined second cumulants $(\mathcal{C}_{13}\mathcal{C}_{23}\mathcal{C}_{12})^{1/2}$, both plotted versus t^* . An interesting feature observed in Fig. 6 is that the Monte Carlo errors are greatest for the case $\tau^* = 10^5$ at which the triple cumulant has switched from negative to positive. The same feature is also observed for the results at $r^* = 50$ in Fig. 1 of the Main Text. The increase in Monte Carlo error for the same sample size implies an increase in the variance, which is tempting to attribute to the variation as realizations switch between triple products with positive and negative values. Note in Fig. 7 that the Monte Carlo error are consistently much smaller for the second cumulants than they are for the triple cumulants, just as was found for the results at $r^* = 50$ in the End Matter, Fig.3.

FIG. 4 Three-point skewness for the vertical equilateral triangle with $r^* = 50$ and vanishing concentration gradient, $\tau^* = 10^4, 10^6, 10^8,$ and 10^{10} . This is an extension of Figure 2 of the Main Text. Solid lines with symbols and shades represent numerical results while dashed lines the analytical prediction.

FIG. 5 Three-point skewness for the vertical equilateral triangle with $r^* = 100$ and vanishing concentration gradient, $\tau^* = 10^4, 10^6,$ and 10^8 . Solid lines with symbols and shades represent numerical results while the red dashed line is the asymptotic analytical prediction in the limit of vanishing gradient.

FIG. 6 Triple cumulant for the vertical equilateral triangle with $r^* = 100$ and vanishing concentration gradient, $\tau^* = 10^4, 10^5, 10^6, 10^7$, and 10^8 . Solid lines with symbols and shades represent numerical results while dashed lines the analytical prediction.

FIG. 7 Average second cumulant for the vertical equilateral triangle with $r^* = 100$ and vanishing concentration gradient, $\tau^* = 10^4, 10^6$, and 10^8 . Solid lines with symbols and shades represent numerical results while dashed lines the analytical prediction. The Monte Carlo error is too small to be visible at this scale.

D. CONCISE COMPARISON OF LIQUID DIFFUSION AND TURBULENT ADVECTION

Our results deepen the analogy between high-Schmidt liquid diffusion and turbulent advection of a passive scalar, which was first proposed by Donev, Fai and Vanden-Eijnden [8]. The latter paper first pointed out that a macroscopic diffusivity renormalized by thermal velocity fluctuations closely resembles an “eddy diffusivity” in a turbulent flow and can be explained by a similar cascade mechanism. This correspondence is not perfect. For example, in a turbulent scalar cascade there is a “dissipative anomaly” so that the effective dissipation rate at high Reynolds numbers becomes completely independent of the microscale parameters such as the bare diffusivity D_0 . By contrast, the Stokes-Einstein relation $D = k_B T / 6\pi\eta\sigma$ for macroscopic diffusivity involves the radius σ of the solute particles and the limit $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ cannot be taken. Thus, as observed already by [8], some small “bare diffusivity” D_0 is required at the finest scale σ where a hydrodynamic approximation is admissible. These differences stem from the fact that the energy spectrum of turbulent velocity fluctuations is peaked at the lowest wavenumbers, so that the turbulent velocities are spatially Hölder continuous, whereas thermal velocity fluctuations have a spectrum peaked at the highest wavenumber and their Hölder exponent is formally negative. We find that advection by such a rough thermal velocity produces non-Gaussian scalar statistics just as does turbulent advection, but all of our derived scaling is consistent with naive dimensional analysis. Thus, there is no signature in our results of “zero modes” [9] and associated anomalous scaling of the higher-order scalar statistics, which is a principal feature of turbulent-advected scalars [2–4].

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